

A THEORETICAL STUDY ON SOCIAL, EMOTIONAL AND EDUCATIONAL PROBLEMS OF ADOLESCENTS

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Abstract:

Adolescence is that period of life where individual face various problems. It is a very important period of human life where adolescents learn enormous knowledge and explore new experience. An individual passes from childish habits of behavior and attitudes to mature one. The adolescents experience strong cognitive, emotional, behavioral and physical changes which occur for the first time in their lives. There are some basic problems of adolescence e.g. development of identity, the growth of interest in opposite sex etc. In a natural way children's experience various problems like- social, emotional, educational, adjustment problem etc. in this stage and these problems have great effect upon their personality factors. Thus in this stage the child need to properly guide which will help in healthy adjustment and develop positive attitude towards their life. In this stage a child starts to realize the practical world and try to

cope up with reality. The focus of the paper is to study the social, emotional and educational problems of adolescents and some solutions to overcome their problems.

Keywords: Adolescence, Enormous Knowledge, Social Problems, Emotional Problems, Educational Problems

1.0 Introduction:

Adolescence is that period of life where individual face various problems. It is a very important period of human life where adolescents learn enormous knowledge and explore new experience. It is a time which starts at the end of childhood and in this stage behavioral and physical change emerge and also ends at the beginning of adulthood. Specially In this stage rapid change take place in the individual's physical, mental, social, emotional, moral, spiritual, sexual etc. In this stage human personality develops new dimensions in this stage and learns new things. It is also a time of behavioral, health problems, depression, conflicts and complexities. Sometimes, this period is called teenage because this period runs between childhood and adulthood.

In this stage remarkable growth, development and changes occurs in every aspect. The adolescents experience strong cognitive, emotional, behavioral and physical changes which occur for the first time in their lives. After the parents the importance of peer group is unavoidable in adolescence because children's find the status in adolescents and improve their feeling of belongingness.

There are some basic problems of adolescence e.g. development of identity, the growth of interest in opposite sex etc. "While in early adolescence (12-14) same-sex friendships prevail, in later adolescence (15-18) there is increased heterosexual interest"(DEVI, 1998). In this stage the child desired to make good impression on others, freedom, self direction, highly self conscious and to be emancipated from the control of parents. Finally in this stage the child seeks meaning in life and build up a sense of values.

Havighurst(1953)introduced a developmental task as that which arises "at about a certain period in the life of an individual, successful achievement of which leads to his happiness and to success with later tasks, while failure leads to unhappiness in the individual, disapproval by society, and difficulty with later tasks."(Havighurst, 1953)

Developmental psychologists G. Stanly Hall in the year 1904 began the study of adolescence with the publication of two volume composition 'Adolescence' (Herlock 1985) in which discussed the period of adolescence as a legitimate phase of life. Stanley Hall (1916) was the first psychologist to advance a psychology of adolescence who has frequently been the father of "Psychology of Adolescence". After experiences with young people and their expressed problems as a result, 'Adolescence' is described as a period of storm and stress. In a natural way children's experience various problems like- social, emotional, educational, adjustment problem etc. in this stage and these problems have great effect upon their personality factors.

Thus in this stage the child need to properly guide which will help in healthy adjustment and develop positive attitude towards their life.

2.0 Meaning of Adolescence:

The period of a person's lifespan between puberty and maturity or adulthood is known as adolescence. Generally we can say the teenage years. Adolescence is an interim phase of growth and development between childhoods to adulthood. It includes many changes like, to the body, structure, size, voice and to the way a young person socializes or relates to the world.

The period between being a child and a mature adult is Adolescence and it is the time during which a person grows into an adult. Generally adolescence corresponds to the teenager years of 13-19 which are so called because the end of the English words "thirteen" to "nineteen".

Adolescence begins with "puberty" It is a period of rapid physical changes and growth. In this stage a boy or girl will sexually mature and boys and girls affects differently. "Puberty" the word derived from a Latin word "pubertas". It means "age of manhood". Reproduction capacity and the sexual appearance are occurring in adolescence period.

In the period of adolescence, children's become extremely self conscious of their various needs like physical appearance, placements in social set up etc. a child passes from their childish habits, behavior and attitude to mature one. An individual passes from childish habits of behavior and attitudes to mature one. Maturity is the ability to respond properly according to the situation and acquire the quality of self control, responsibility, realistic view of life etc. Many psychologists described this stage in their own way. There are some definition given by well known psychologists are given bellow-

According to Jean Peaget, "Adolescence is the age of great ideals and the beginning of theories as well as the time of simple adaptation to reality."(Gentry, 2006)

According to S. Hall, "Adolescence is a period of great stresses and strains, storm and strife" (Hall, 1904)

According to Arthur T. Jersild, "Adolescence is that span of years during which boys and girls move from childhood to adulthood, mentally, socially, emotionally"(Mihalyi, 2019)

From the above definition it very well may be said that "adolescence" is a very broad concept that include physical maturity, mental maturity, emotional maturity, as well as the realistic view of life. It is the very important stage of life because a child starts to realize the practical world and try to cope up with reality.

3.0 Review of related literature:

Literature review is a very important part of a study because it is a handy guide to particular topic. Literature review helps researcher to have a comprehensive knowledge and idea of the topic and literature available in the field which study is being taken up. From the related literature it is observed that "this is the period of physiological change. It is the period when

children become sexually mature. It is also the period of intensified personal interaction with peers of the same and opposite sex.”(Tegelman et al., 1990) During adolescence, “the individual has to achieve a masculine or feminine social role; accept one's physique and use the body effectively; achieve emotional independence of parents and other adults; achieve assurance of economic independence by selecting and preparing for an occupation; prepare for marriage and family life; develop intellectual skills and concepts necessary for civic competence; achieve socially responsible behaviour; acquire a set of values and an ethical system as a guide to behaviour.”(DEVI, 1998) “Adolescence is the period of physiological upheaval, of tremendous bodily, especially sexual maturation. It is also the period of intensified personal interactions with peers, of the same and opposite sex and with leader figures.”(Laxmi, 1998) “Children and adolescents exposed to violence may develop mental health problems, impacting their ability to develop appropriate social-emotional skills.”(Aviles et al., 2006) “Social-emotional competence is defined as cooperative and pro-social behaviour, initiation and maintenance of peer friendships and adult relationships, management of aggression and conflict, development of a sense of mastery and self-worth and emotional regulation and reactivity” (Squires, 2002). “The problem of adolescence is by no means an easy topic to discuss it is often said that the teenage years are the “best years of one’s life”. “Life for many adolescents is a painful tug of war filled with mixed messages and conflicting demands from parents, teachers, friends, family and oneself. Growing up—negotiating a path between independence and reliance on others—is a tough business.”(Kumari, n.d.)

4.0 Problems of Adolescence:

Adolescence is the most important period when a child develops independently. In this period children try to prove their independence by asking their parents rule and also believe that they are right and try to prove themselves. So this time is very challenging for parents also to control. In this phase of life adolescent face various challenges or problems. They face various physical, social, emotional, educational problems. Here we discuss about various adolescents problem in various aspects;

4.1 Social Problems of Adolescence:

Every society and culture has its own traditions, customs, rituals and practices that it wants to preserve. Every individual is required to follow the societal ideals and values but many adolescents often refuse to obey and think that these are outdated. These results to conflict and children’s face various problems in adjustment. In this period because of these conflicts a number of social problems take place.

a) **Problem of social adjustment:** In this stage, adolescents face adjustment problem. The physical structure of adolescent develops very fast. The height, weight, other body organs develop very fast and these changes create tension among adolescents. They need proper care and diet at that time. Both boys and girls voice change, boy’s voice become hard, and girl’s voice become sharp and shrill. These physical changes feel uncomfortable to adjust with people and sometime they develop shyness among them.

b) **Drug and substance abuse:** Adolescence is that phase of life where they are vulnerable and can be easily swayed to the wrong side. In this stage, adolescents don't think of their actions today and the results of tomorrow. Drug and substance abuse is one of the biggest problems that parents of adolescents around the world have to deal with. This is happen because of various reasons like peer pressure, tendency to take risk, family influences, poor self esteem etc. So it is the duty of parents to show the right path to their children.

c) **Bullying:** Bullying is an aggressive behavior that is intended to show power and control over another person. It is another social problem of adolescents they face at this age. A child become a bully because of various factors like peer rejection, failure, abuse, neglect by others, low self esteem etc. People who have victim of bullying they suffered various problems like mental health problem, anxiety, depression, anti social personality etc.

d) **Rebellious attitude:** The adolescents are not more child in this stage. They should recognize as a young men and women in the school, home, as well as in the society. Their craving for independence should be satisfied to some extent if not then they feel left out and alone. They should be given some responsibility so that they feel their identity as gentle men as well as a woman.

4.2 Emotional Problems:

During the period of adolescence the Childs emotional development reaches its maximum .In this stage they heightening all their emotions like anger, anxiety, fear, love etc. Because of this adolescence experience various problems and they don't have sufficient control on their emotions. Various emotional problem of adolescence are like;

- a) **Stress and depression:** Depression is one of the most common mental illnesses and now a day the people have mental health problem increase day by day worldwide. In adolescent period the adolescents face this problem because of various causes like peer pressure, changing hormone levels and developing bodies. Depression associated with stress and anxiety which may affect various aspects of their life: personal life, social life. Sometimes stress and anxiety causes isolation, decrease energy, difficulty concentrating and misuse of drug or alcohol.
- b) **Aggressiveness:** In this stage lack of emotional stability adolescent become aggressive and emotional. Aggression take in many forms; social, verbal, physical and sometimes it become violence. They react frequently on others action and these actions creates gap between them. When adolescent cannot adjust themselves with the world they grow aggressiveness from the field.
- c) **Confusion about their identity:** Adolescence is the age between adulthood and childhood. Here adolescent are often confused about their role and between their responsibilities as growing adults and their desires as children they face identity problem as who I am?
- d) **Sexual problem:** In this stage adolescent sexual development reaches its peak and face challenges because of this. Feelings and thoughts about sex can trigger a sense of guilt

in them. Sexual feeling may increase and they want to experience it and sometimes engage in sexual behavior without realizing consequence.

4.3 Educational Problems:

- a) **Pressure to performance:** In this stage adolescents feel pressure. They want to do their best to make their own identity but sometimes lack of proper guidance brings failure to them. They also face challenges to get college admission and if did not get any good college then it can be stressful and make teenager moody.
- b) **The peer pressure:** This is the most faced problem by adolescents in academic field. In school or colleges they have to do many activities in which they are no interested. Many students are forced into activities such as dance, sports, drama, debate etc only because of peer pressure. Following their friend some parents also forced their children to do such type of activities without knowing their children's interest. Sometimes doing activities in peer pressure is good but sometime it gives negative effect to the child and then they will not able to concentrate on studies which affect their academic field.
- c) **Drop out:** Another educational problem among adolescents is drop out. Though adolescence is the period of acquiring new knowledge but when we see to the practical field then we noticed that many students drop out from school at this stage. There is various reason of dropout as bad influence of friends, fail to fulfill academic challenges, health issues, want to earn money etc. But we can minimize the drop out tendency among adolescence by parenting involvement, encourage and motivate them, teach values of life.
- d) **Problem of Leisure:** Generally leisure is a free time which perceived freedom and choice. Leisure is an experience which give emphasizes of perceived freedom and it should be use in a purposeful activity. Lack of proper engage in activity or having nothing to do in their leisure time or free times children's involve in various unsocial as well as criminal activities. Because of this thought adolescents create destructive and problems for themselves as well as for the society.

5.0 How Adolescence Can Deal With Their Problem:

The most difficult period of individual's life is the period of adolescence as physically, mentally, socially as well as emotionally. To overcome from their problems and to cope up with their situation here parental influences has much important. Parents should know about what is going on in their child's life and they also have to concern about the adolescents problems. Participation in family activities, setting clear and fair rules, understanding peer influences in adolescents life, availability to give help when needed or asked for can helps the adolescents to great extent.

5.1 Solution of Social Problem:

- I. Involve your child in various social activities so that they can adjust with the situation easily.
- II. As a parent it is the duty of parents to ensure and understand the importance of sex to their child.

- III. Develop habit of yoga, meditation, walking etc. These habits will help them to develop their quality of love, care, happiness, discipline etc. and help them to control their aggressive nature.
- IV. Sharing parent's social life experience with children also helps them to ease their difficult problem to easy one and give them strength to stand as a strong one.

5.2 Solution of Emotional Problem:

- I. Involve your child in creative activities like art, music, drama etc. It can help them channelize their emotions.
- II. Share your own experience of your adolescent period and as well as their elder brother or sisters story of this period. It will help them to strong their emotional capacity and it will give them belief that it is okay to feel the way they do.
- III. Listen to your child when they want to talk. Give importance and listen to them without advice and judging them when they are not ready to listen.

5.3 Solution of Educational Problem:

- I. Support your children and help them when they need. Understand the need and interest of children and give education according this.
- II. Support and respect child's aspiration for education and encourage them to choose their favorite subject.
- III. Aware them about importance of nutrition and make healthy habit of daily exercise so that they get strength to cope up with the hectic school period.
- IV. Minimize the household chores of children to enable them to focus on their educational work.
- V. Adolescents should use their leisure time in an effective way by doing extracurricular activities, work oriented tasks for pleasure, good relationship with others, sports, reading, meditation etc. which is for long term utility

6.0 Conclusion:

Adolescence period is the crucial period as adolescents go through profound physical, mental, social, emotional changes. These changes bring various problems to them. But love, care, understanding works as a medicine to them in solving different problems of their lives. Proper care and knowledge of adolescent problem would help the parents and teachers and other member of society to help those problems of adolescents to overcome their problems and to develop a healthy and strong personality. Because adolescent is the period of cherished and sunshine and everyone has to try enjoy this period as enjoyable period of life.

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